

Corporate Governance and Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya: A Critical Review of Literature

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Abstract

the purpose of this paper is to critically review the existing literature on the relationship between corporate governance and the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The corporate governance attributes of board composition, board independence, board gender and audit committee independence were used as independent variables. Financial performance was measured using Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Profitability Margin (PM) and Tobin's Q. The studies reviewed both theoretical and empirical literature. The studies were based on three theories; Agency Theory, Stewardship Theory and Resource Dependency Theory. The studies revealed that board size, board independence and audit committee independence have a positive and significant relationship with the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. However, board composition and board gender have a negative relationship with financial performance. The studies concluded that corporate governance structures improve the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The studies recommend that the management of the commercial bank in Kenya should implement strong corporate governance structures in order to achieve good financial performance.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Financial Performance, Commercial Banks

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The effect of corporate governance on financial performance has received enormous attention in economics and finance literature in recent years. This attention has been motivated by financial scandals that rocked the US economy in late 2000 and the Asian financial crisis of the 1990s. In Kenya, the wave of mergers, acquisitions and collapse of banks came as a wakeup call to the Central Bank of Kenya to strengthen supervision arm CBK (2001).

Corporate governance from a managerial perspective refers to the controls used to ensure that managers' actions are consistent with the interest of key constituent shareholders (Hill & Jones, 2001). The aim of corporate governance is to facilitate the efficient use of resources by reducing fraud and mismanagement with the view not only to maximize but also to align the often conflicting interests of all stakeholders (Cadbury, 1999; King Report, 2002).

In these studies, corporate governance structures are represented by five attributes; board composition, board independence, board size, board gender and audit committee independence. These are the independent variables. Financial performance was measured by return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) profitability margin and Tobin's Q.

Currently, in Kenya, the number of licensed banks is 42 (CBK, 2018). Commercial banks receive deposits from individuals and then lend these funds in the form of loans to other customers at high interest rate thereby earning a profit.

2.0 Theoretical Review

The concept of corporate governance has been explained by three theories; Agency theory, Stewardship theory and Resource dependence theory.

2.1 Agency Theory

Empirical studies on corporate governance have been based on an agency theory perspective. This is because corporate governance has a root in agency theory (Wright 2011). The principal-agent relationship

originates when a principal hires an agent to perform a service or to act on his behalf (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Managers in a firm are agents of shareholders who assume that the principles guiding them are those geared towards maximization of shareholders' wealth. However, there are three factors that disturb this relationship. In the first place, there is a conflict of interest between the principal and the agent. The agents may strive to maximize their own utility at the expense of the principals, secondly, the presence of a high level of information asymmetry between the principal and the agent and the possibility that the agent can take advantage of this information asymmetry to enrich themselves and lastly the inability of the principal to ensure that the agent acts in compliance with his or her interests that make it impossible or too expensive for him or her to monitor the efforts of the agent.

The divergence behavior between the interests of the principle and those of the agent give rise to agency costs. The idea behind agency theory is to select whatever mechanism that will regulate the relationship between the agent and the principal in a manner that will ensure alignment of the interests of the two parties leading to a reduction of agency costs. These mechanisms may take the form of contracts that may be implied or written that are based on a number of assumptions about people (self-interest, limited rationality, risk aversion).

Jensen (1986), argues that there is earning retention conflict between managers and shareholders of a firm. Whereas managers would prefer to retain the company's earnings with a view of investing in the next available positive net present value projects, shareholders would prefer higher returns in the form of cash dividends paid to them. This scenario is more prevalent in companies characterized by fewer internal positive net present value investment opportunities. Managers in these companies stand to benefit from retained earnings in the following related ways: high amount of retained earnings grants them a larger power base, large retained earnings provide them with greater prestige and large retained earnings can provide them with the ability to dominate the board and award them higher remunerations. Managers of companies who are risk averse prefer higher equity financing in their companies' capital structure than debt. This is because debt increases the risk of default and bankruptcy that may expose their weaknesses. In the absence of sufficient equity, they would prefer the use of retained earnings in their financing plans. Despite the fact that retained earnings as a source of financing reduce the need for external financing, in case managers require more funds for investment purposes, they have to go to the external markets where they have to incur floatation costs. These costs are known to provide a useful monitoring mechanism that constraint a manager from investing in negative net present value projects.

Agency theory has been criticized that directors as agents act in their own self-interest but managers are also interested in the long term survival of their companies. They make decisions that benefit the company in the long run. The shareholders, on the other hand, also have an interest in the growth of their share value. Therefore, they do not necessarily prefer cash dividends.

2.2 Stewardship Theory

If anyone is to consider a theory that can motivate managers, stewardship theory comes in handy as an alternative to agency theory. Stewardship theory replaces the absence of trust in agency theory with respect to authority and fondness to ethical behaviors geared at boosting firm performance (Clarke, 2004). The ultimate intention that drives managers to accomplish their jobs is underlined in their desire to perform satisfactorily. Managers are conjured up as being motivated by the need to achieve, the need to gain intrinsic satisfaction through successfully performing challenging tasks and the need to exercise responsibility and authority that makes them gain recognition from their peers and seniors (Donaldson & Davis 1991). The main objective bestowed on managers in a firm is primarily to maximize shareholders' wealth. It is widely acknowledged that this objective can well be achieved when firms under their management perform exemplarily well. Davis *et al.* (1997) contend that managers left on their own will act as responsible stewards of the company's assets under their control. Stewardship theorists further argue that there is a need for organizations to put in place structures that allow harmonization of objectives that managers and shareholders of firms need to achieve if superior performance is to be realized. Stewardship theory not only focuses on the CEO's motivation but rather on facilitative empowering structures that fusion the incumbency

roles of the chairman and CEO of the company that enhances effectiveness leading to the achievement of superior performance.

2.3 Resource Dependency Theory

Resource dependency theory provides a theoretical foundation for the role of the board of directors as a resource to the firm (Wagana, 2015). The theory appreciates the strategic importance of other stakeholders besides the immediate shareholders in guaranteeing a firm's access to resources through affiliation with various constituencies (Lawal, 2012). The role of the board of directors under the resource dependency model is that the directors use individual external networks of contacts to attract resources that the firm needs to operate competitively and advance superior performance. The focus of the resource dependency theory is on the role directors' play in securing essential resources to an organization through their linkages to the external environment. Johnson (1996) observed that Resource Dependence theorists provide a focus for the appointment of representatives of independent organizations as a means for gaining access to resources critical to firm success.

Pfeffer (1972) stated that board size and background of outside directors are important to managing the organization's needs for capital and regulatory environment. Hillman, (2000) opines that directors bring resources to the firm, such as information, skills, access to key constituents such as suppliers, public policymakers and social groups. Other scholars used the resource dependency theory to explain the composition of boards especially in terms of outsider representation (Bathula, 2008). Pearce and Zahra (1992) submit that outsiders are appointed to the board in order to bring a fresh perspective when a firm is not doing well. It can also be argued that female members on the board benefit the firm's governance through an influx of skills, abilities and fresh perspectives by bringing in new dynamics to board deliberations (Jamali et al., 2007).

From a resource dependency theory perspective, it can be predicted that a well-diversified board improves performance.

3.0 Empirical Review

Several studies have been done regarding corporate governance and the financial performance of commercial banks.

Al – Manaseer et al. (2012) empirically investigated corporate governance on the performance of Jordanian banks listed on the Amman Stock Exchange for the period 2007 to 2009. The study employed panel data and ordinary least squares estimation method with panel data methodology. Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Profit Margin (PM) and Earnings per Share (EPS) were adopted as performance measures (dependable variables) whereas board size, CEO status, foreign ownership and bank size were adopted as independent variables.

The study revealed a significant negative relationship between Board size and Bank performance as measured by Return on Equity (ROE) and Earnings per Share (EPS). The study also revealed a positive association between Board independence and Bank performance as measured by ROE, ROA, PM and EPS. It is only bank size that was significant and positively related to EPS.

Kusi et al. (2016) empirically studied the effect of corporate governance structures on shareholders' value maximization in African Banks. They sampled 270 banks in 29 countries in Africa from 2006 to 2011. He used panel data from bank scope and World Development Indicators databases. The study employed an ordinary least squares regression model. ROE and ROA were adopted as performance measures (dependent variables). Board size, board independence, board composition, board gender and audit committee independence were adopted as independent variables. Bank size was used as a control variable. The study revealed that board size is positively and significantly related to financial performance in banks in Africa. That is, an increase in bank board size leads to an increase in bank shareholder value. The study also

established that board composition is negatively and significantly related to financial performance. This implies that good corporate governance structures negatively affect financial performance.

With regard to audit committee independence, the study found out that there is a positive and significant relationship.

Bank size measured as a log of total assets reports a positive and significant relationship with the shareholder's value. An increase in bank size leads to an increase in shareholders' value.

Board independence is negatively and significantly related to shareholder value. That is, banks that have their CEOs being the board chairman are likely to experience a reduction in bank profitability.

Nyarige (2012), sought to analyze how corporate governance structures of commercial banks in Kenya affect their financial performance. The focus of the study was on the nine commercial banks listed on NSE between 2005 and 2010. Board size, board meetings, board independence and executive compensation were adopted as independent variables while Tobin's Q ratio was adopted as a proxy for financial performance (dependent variable). The research was conducted using a Cross-sectional survey that sought to identify differences in corporate governance's structures between listed banks facing a decline in values, those facing appreciating values and those with stable value on calendar years 2005 to 2010. The findings of the study indicated that board size negatively affects the banks' market performance, while board independence affects the banks' market performance positively.

Wepukhulu (2016) studied the relationship between corporate governance and performance of a commercial bank in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive research design in analysing the relationship between corporate governance and performance in commercial banks in Kenya for the period spanning 2001-2013. A survey was conducted in all the 43 commercial banks that were licensed and operating in Kenya as of 31st December 2013. The study adopted ROA, ROE and Tobin's Q as performance measures (Dependent variables). He used board size, board independence institutional ownership and block ownership as independent variables. Bank size was used as a control variable.

Structured questionnaires were used as primary data collection tools. Secondary data was collected from audited annual financial reports for individual banks found on the bank website at the registrar of companies' offices at Attorney General Chambers Nairobi, Nairobi Securities Exchange and at the Central Bank website and library. The study used hierarchical multiple regression model. The results indicated that there is a negative correlation between board size and performance of commercial banks in Kenya. There is no correlation between board independence and performance when ROE is adopted as a performance measure.

4.0 Critique of Existing Literature Relevant to the Study

A number of studies have been carried out to assess the relationship between corporate governance and performance of banking firms in different parts of the world. However, they manifest a number of weaknesses, as discussed below:

Al – Manaseer et al. (2012), in their study on the effect of corporate governance on bank performance, used Earnings per Share (EPS), Profit Margin (PM), Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) as key performance measures. The same measures were used by Kusi et al. (2016). However, EPS is not the best measure of comparative performance because different banks have different capital structures. It is also difficult to obtain the company's number of outstanding shares at a given period in time to enable one to ascertain the firm's EPS because trading cannot be stopped. The profit margin, on the other hand, is derived from profitability figures of the firm hence suffers from setbacks profit as a measure of performance suffers.

Al – Manaseer et al. (2012) also adopted bank size as a proxy for corporate governance when, indeed, it should be adopted as a moderating variable.

Nyarige (2012) adopted Tobin's Q as a financial performance measure while it is known that Tobin's Q is a market measure of performance. The findings of the study indicated that board size negatively affects the

banks' market performance, while board independence affects the banks' market performance positively. Given that the performance measure adopted is not a financial measure of performance; no findings with respect to the study were made. Therefore the specific objective of the study was not achieved.

Wepukhulu (2016) adopted ROA, ROE and Tobin's Q as performance measures (dependent variables). ROA and ROE depend on earnings (profits), which presents a measurement problem. Tobin's Q is regarded as a measure of market performance and not financial performance. The study also included bank size as the only control variable and yet there are other moderating variables such as leverage, ownership structure and risk management.

4.1 Research Gaps

Studies relating to corporate governance and financial performance have yielded contradictory and inconclusive results. Some studies have documented positive relationships while others have reported either negative or no relationship. The possible explanation for the conflicts and contradictions could be that intervention and moderation effects are excluded from the studies, the differences in the attributes of the predictor dependent variable used, as well as methodological differences.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

From the results, it is evident that corporate governance structures affect the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Board size positively influences bank value maximization to shareholders. The study also identified that good corporate governance in the form of an independent audit committee promotes and protects shareholder value maximization. The study further finds that board independence leads to better financial performance. The study finds that board composition is negatively related to financial performance. It means that the increase in non-executive board members will lead to diverse ideas and opinions leading to board room struggles and prolonged deliberations on matters which slow decision making. This negatively affects financial performance.

5.2 Recommendations

These findings have relevant and practical implications for commercial banks in Kenya. First, commercial bank management must implement good governance structures to improve financial performance and avoid weak corporate governance structures. Also, in an attempt to improve financial performance, commercial banks in Kenya must not only focus on instituting good governance structures but also consider bank-specific and macroeconomic factors such as bank size, credit risk, management quality and diversification. Previous studies have, in many instances, used earnings as a financial performance measure. Future studies should be based on the CAMEL model (Capital adequacy, Asset quality, management capacity, Earnings and Liquidity).

Future research can be done on corporate governance and financial performance, putting into consideration moderating and intervening variables such as risk management and firm characteristics.

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